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A SYSTEMATIC APPROACH TO FAMILY FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT- AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Financial management within the family is a hard nut to crack for many of the home-runners. Though the income is high, several families find they run out of financial resources and helpless at emergency situations. Proper financial management within the family and maintaining the financial health is essential to be well supplied with economical resources when in need. It is because of the failure in managing the financial resources many families get bound to bank loans, and often bankruptcy. Improper management of wealth sources will raise possible risks in life and will create unwanted situations in life. Managing money is not a tough concept, if approached well and remained adhered to the budget and decisions constantly. Many people never consider or foresee the possible future expenses and drain out all the savings and resources for present day life. If reserved a bit of extra consciousness on the money matters, maintaining a healthy financial family is a possible task.

Keyword: Budget, Family, Financial Health, Financial management, and Knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

Management is an indispensable part of family living; some families do manage their affairs well while some manage them poorly. However, success of family living depends on how well the resources are managed. In general the concept of management may be said to be planned activities directed towards accomplishing desired goals. The use made of the family's resources and extent to which family goals are achieved largely depends on how well they are managed and also on the managerial ability, interest and leadership of the homemakers and their ability to motivate all the members of the group.

In modern family, financial management is a collective responsibility of both the male and female heads as in one way or other both are involved. The financial management has become a joint venture of husband and wife. Rising of financial resources and other funds and the effective utilization of the above depends on the effective financial management. Hence, an attempt has been made to analyze the financial management of the family.

SCOPE

Ludhiana is an important place in the economic history of Punjab. It is an industrial district and has a population from all walks of life. But it is generally believed that the financial management and financial awareness is till today not up to the mark. So the study aims to present financial management of families in Ludhiana district.

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the study is to analyze the financial management of families in Ludhiana district of Punjab.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study involves both primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected from the sample respondents by using the questionnaire. The required secondary data was collected from the revenue office of Ludhiana district, Websites and publication of the Government of Punjab. This is a case study which as one of the survey methods is a very popular form adopted for qualitative analysis and involves a careful and complete observation of a social unit, be that unit a person, a family, an institution, a cultural group or even the entire community. A sample of 250 respondents was taken. The researcher contacted the heads of the families for collection of data. The respondents were selected using the techniques of simple random sampling method with the help of family ration cards distributed by the revenue official. Simple random sampling involves selecting samples by random chance mechanism, such that every sample has an equal and independent chance of being selected.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis in respect of financial management of the sample families have been presented in the following paragraphs.

PREPARATION OF FAMILY BUDGET

Budget is a plan for spending and saving within a given income for a definite period. The family estimates its income in relation to the various wants that the family has. It may be described as a financial plan for future expenditure. Table 1 describes how the respondents taken for this study prepare their family budget.

TABLE 1
Preparation of Budget

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Written	65	26.1
Oral	185	73.9
Total	250	100.0

Table 1 shows the way in which the budget is prepared. Of the total respondents, 73.9 per cent prepare the budget orally, whereas 26.1 per cent prepare written budget.

MANAGEMENT OF FAMILY BUDGET

The budget is sometimes considered as the whole of money management and this is misconception. It is only the planning step. Management means also controlling and evaluating. Controlling is what is being spent and how, and evaluating whether the expenditure is in conformity with the allocation of the budget. So the importance lies not only in the preparation of budget but also is in management of it. Table 2 displays who manage the family budget.

TABLE 2
Management of Family Budget

Person Managing The Budget	Frequency	Percentage
Husband	53	21.3
Wife	40	15.8
Jointly By Husband and Wife	124	49.7
Elders	14	5.5
Others	19	7.7
Total	250	100.0

From the Table 2 it is inferred that 49.7 per cent of the respondent’s household manage the family budget ‘jointly by husband and wife’ followed by 21.3 per cent by ‘husband’ only. It is further seen that elders and others are not considered in this matter.

TYPE OF BUDGET

Table 3 and 4 highlight the type of budget that the respondents make in their day to day life. It should be based on period as well as income. Table 3 shows the period of budget.

TABLE 3
Period of Budget

Period	Frequency	Percentage
Daily	39	15.7
Weekly	17	6.7
Monthly	164	65.5
Annually	30	12.1
Total	250	100.0

It is inferred from Table 3 that 65.5 per cent of the respondents prepares monthly budget, while 15.7 per cent prepare daily budget and only 12.1 per cent prepare annual budget.

TABLE 4
Income and Budget

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Surplus	62	24.6
Deficit	64	25.6
Balanced	124	49.8
Total	250	100.0

Table 4 describes whether the income goes along with the preparation of the budget. Of the total respondents 49.8 per cent says that they have 'balanced' budget followed by 25.6 per cent says as 'deficit' and 24.6 per cent says it is 'surplus'.

BUDGET PLAN

No budget can be rigid. Budget is plan for future and this can be altered by so many factors such as unforeseen expenditure, sudden illness. Table 5 explains whether the budget prepared by the respondents is fixed or not.

TABLE 5
Budget Plan

Description	Frequency	Percentage
Fixed/Rigid	62	25.0
Flexible	188	75.0
Total	250	100.0

It is inferred from the Table 5 that 75 per cent of the respondents says that they have flexible budget and the rest of 25 per cent says it is fixed.

REASON FOR FLEXIBILITY

The reason for flexibility of budget has been attempted. It may arise due to unforeseen circumstances and one cannot adhere strictly to the budgetary practices. After a careful study, five possible reasons have been identified for the deviation from the prepared budget. It is depicted in Table 6

TABLE 6
Reasons For Flexibility

Reason	Yes		Rank
	Frequency	%	
Impulse Buying	136	54.5	II
Unexpected Expenditure	188	75.0	I
Lack of Experience and skills	60	23.9	IV
Lack of Cooperation by Family member	59	23.7	VI
Improper Planning	75	29.9	III
Not Understanding the Budgetary Procedure	60	23.8	V

It could be seen from Table 6 that the reason for flexibility may vary from one family to another. Most of the heads of families have pointed out the reason 'unexpected expenditure' and it accounted for 75 per cent. Hence, it is placed in first rank and followed this they have placed the second position to 'impulse buying' 54.5 per cent. The third rank go to 'improper planning'. The remaining reasons are ranked according to the descending order of merit.

OPINION ABOUT BUDGETING OF THE FAMILY INCOME

Planning enables a family to take an overview of their use of income, thus seeing it in perspective and helps to live within one's income. After a careful scrutiny, five major reasons were given to the respondents for selection. Since it is a multi-response question, ranking analysis has been done. Table 7 describes the opinion of the respondents.

TABLE 7
Opinion about Budgeting of the Family Income

Opinion	Yes		Rank
	Frequency	%	
Gives Clear Picture of the use of income	207	82.9	I
Helps to Meet Family Needs and Wants	183	73.0	V
Fulfill Future Needs	198	79.1	III
Improve Economic Position and Standard of Living	202	80.8	II
Helps to Save	193	77.2	IV

When the respondents are asked to give opinion for budgeting, a vast majority of respondents 82.9 per cent have opined that it gives clear picture of the use of income. So, this opinion has been placed in first position which is clear from Table 7. The next rank is placed in respect of the opinion 'improve economic position and standard of living' and third goes to 'fulfil future needs'. The opinions 'helps to save' and 'helps to meet family needs and wants' have been placed in fourth and fifth ranks respectively.

REASONS FOR NOT FOLLOWING THE BUDGET

Due to various reasons, one is not able to adhere to the budget prepared by the family. The most possible reasons for not following the budget have been listed out for getting responses from the sample respondents and the result are illustrated in Table 8

TABLE 8
Reasons for Not Following the Budget

Reasons	Yes		Rank
	Frequency	%	
Lack of Time	117	46.5	I
Lack of Experience and Skill	79	31.5	V
Lack of Knowledge	70	28.1	VI
Not able to follow Strictly the Budget	106	42.5	III
Income is not Sufficient	116	46.4	II
Lack of Cooperation by Family Members	84	33.5	IV

The above Table 8 describes the reasons for not following the budget in financial management of family. The first and the foremost reason goes to 'lack of time'. Around 46.5 per cent of respondents pointed out this reason. This is because of improper planning and work force tightened on the family heads. Because of insufficient income, most of them don't want to follow the budget. It works out to 46.4 per cent. This reason has been placed in second position. Third rank assigned to the reason 'not able to follow strictly the budget'. The fourth, fifth and sixth ranks are assigned to the rest of the reasons in the order of merit.

MEETING OF FAMILY EXPENDITURE WITHOUT PLANNED BUDGET

Budgeting required adherence of some factors. It is difficult of most of heads of family. Hence, they run the family without planning also. The following Table 9 reveals about how the family expenditure is met without a planned budget.

TABLE 9
Meeting of Family Expenditure without Planned Budget

Statements	Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
According to the needs and wants of the family	149	59.6	101	40.4
As when income comes in	148	59.1	102	40.9
Meet the expenditure with the amount in hand	144	57.5	106	42.5
Spend on Important items and leave the rest	142	56.7	108	43.3
Discuss with Family Members	141	56.2	110	43.8

It could be seen from Table 9 that that a major portion of respondents 56 per cent says that they manage the family expenditure without a planned budget for all the given five statements. It is 59.6 per cent for the statement 'according to the needs and wants of the family', 59.1 per cent for 'as when income comes in' and 57.5 per cent for 'meet the expenditure with the amount on hand'. Further it is seen that 56.7 per cent stated as 'spend on important items and leave the rest', and 56.2 per cent as 'discuss with family members'. From the survey it is clear that majority of respondents having ability to manage the family expenditure without a planned budget.

PROBLEMS FACED IN MEETING THE FAMILY EXPENDITURE

No family is self sufficient. Whatever may be the income of the family and well planned budgeting, all families face with financial problems.

TABLE 10
Problems Faced in Meeting the Expenditure

Problems	Yes		No	
	Frequency	%	Frequency	%
Cannot meet the needs and wants of the family	145	58.0	105	42.0
Depend on Loan	118	47.1	132	52.9
Not able to account for the money used or spent	117	47.0	133	53.0
Cannot Bring income and expenditure into Balance	132	52.9	118	47.1
Unable to improve the Economic Position and Standard of life	146	58.5	104	41.5
Unable to Save	127	50.9	123	49.1

Table 10 reveals the problems faced by the respondents in meeting the family expenditure. It is understood from Table 10 that 58.5 per cent of respondents faced the problem 'unable to improve the economic position and standard of life', 58 per cent faced 'cannot meet the needs and wants of the family', 52.9 per cent cannot bring income and expenditure into balance' and 50.9 per cent 'unable to save' have been the main reasons faced in meeting the expenditure. Further, it is also clear from Table 10 that around 53 per cent of respondents have not faced the problems 'not able to account for the money used or spent' and 'depend on loan'.

FINDING

From the study it is clear that around 74 per cent of heads of families are preparing oral budget only. The family budget is mostly managed jointly by husband and wife (49.7%) following this around 21.3 per cent of husband managing the family budget. Majority of 65.5 per cent of families are preparing monthly budget and around 50 per cent preparing the balanced budget. The plan of budget is

normally flexible and it accounts for 75 per cent in the study. Unexpected expenditure is the main reason for preparing the flexible budget. Regarding opinion of preparing the budget, most of the respondents opined that it gives clear picture of the use of income. Hence, first rank is assigned to this opinion. 'Lack of time' is the main reason for not following the budget 46.5 per cent and it is positioned in first place. All the five statements chosen in the study are favouring towards meeting of family expenditure without planned budget. The major problems faced by the respondents are unable to improve the economic position and standard of life and cannot meet the needs and wants of the family.

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